

Equilibrium studies on ternary chelates of trivalent metal ions with 2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)benzimidazole, 2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)benzoxazole and other ligands in solution

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Abstract : The pH-metric equilibrium studies of (1 : 1 : 1) ternary chelates, MAL where, M = La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Gd^{III}, Dy^{III} and Y^{III}; L = 2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)benzimidazole and 2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)benzoxazole and A = iminodiacetic acid and nitrilotriacetic acid have been carried out in dioxane-water (50% v/v) medium at 30 °C and 0.1 M (KNO₃) ionic strength. The formation constants of binary complexes (ML and ML₂) are also determined under similar experimental conditions. The formation constants of the ternary complexes, MAL are evaluated and their relative stabilities compared to the corresponding binary complexes are expressed in terms of the statistical parameter, $\Delta \log K$. Various factors influencing the formation and stability of the ternary chelates are discussed.

Keywords : Ternary chelates, formation constants, stability, $\Delta \log K$.

The 2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)benzimidazole and 2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)benzoxazole are known for their numerous analytical¹ and other applications². The synthesis and characterisation of metal chelates of these bidentate (N,O-donor) ligands was reported³. Although these ligands do not have any biological activity, their ternary complexes were found to exhibit biological activity⁴. The formation constants of binary complexes of 2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)benzimidazole in solution were also reported⁵. However, no significant quantitative studies were made on the ternary chelates of these ligands in solution. The present paper reports the pH-metric study of the formation and stability of trivalent (lanthanoid) metal ion ternary chelates, MAL where, M = La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Gd^{III}, Dy^{III} and Y^{III}; L = 2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)benzimidazole (HPBI) and 2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)benzoxazole (HPBO) in presence of A = iminodiacetic acid (IDA) and nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) in 1,4-dioxane-water (50% v/v) medium at 30 °C and 0.1 M (KNO₃) ionic strength.

Results and discussion

Acid-dissociation constants (pK) of ligands : The pK values of all the ligands have been redetermined under present experimental conditions and are presented in Table 1.

Binary systems : The formation constants of (1 : 1) ML

and (1 : 2) ML₂ binary chelates are determined⁶ by analyzing titration curves and experimental data and listed in Table 1. The stabilities of binary complexes were found to be ML > ML₂ as expected on statistical grounds⁷. Their stabilities are also in accordance with the basicities of the ligands, HPBI > HPBO.

Table 1. Acid-dissociation constants of ligands and formation constants of binary complexes in dioxane-water (50% v/v) medium at 30 °C and $\mu = 0.1 M$ (KNO₃)

Ligand/ system	pK ₁	pK ₂	M ^{III} -HPBI		M ^{III} -HPBO	
			log K _{ML} ^M	log K _{ML₂} ^M	log K _{ML} ^M	log K _{ML₂} ^M
HPBI (L)	4.3	11.12				
HPBO (L)	2.1	11.21				
IDA (A)	3.3	9.21				
NTA (A)	3.7	10.01				
La ^{III} -L			7.65	6.98	7.40	6.81
Pr ^{III} -L			7.82	7.37	7.61	7.28
Nd ^{III} -L			8.02	7.39	7.75	7.32
Dy ^{III} -L			8.23	7.42	7.95	7.38
Gd ^{III} -L			8.35	7.51	8.10	7.45
Y ^{III} -L			8.45	7.81	8.21	7.72

(Values are accurate to ± 0.05)

Table 2. Formation constants of ternary complexes in dioxane-water (50% v/v) medium at 30 °C and $\mu = 0.1 M$ (KNO_3)

M^{III}	M^{III} -IDA-HPBI			M^{III} -NTA-HPBI			M^{III} -IDA-HPBO			M^{III} -NTA-HPBO		
	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	$\Delta \log K$	SUBS	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	$\Delta \log K$	SUBS	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	$\Delta \log K$	SUBS	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	$\Delta \log K$	SUBS
La ^{III}	7.13	-0.52	0.642	6.50	-1.15	0.586	7.51	0.11	0.677	6.75	-0.65	0.608
Pb ^{III}	7.26	-0.56	0.654	6.54	-1.28	0.589	7.54	-0.06	0.679	6.82	-0.78	0.614
Nd ^{III}	7.41	-0.61	0.668	6.64	-1.38	0.598	7.61	-0.14	0.686	6.87	-0.88	0.619
Gd ^{III}	7.45	-0.78	0.671	7.02	-1.21	0.632	7.65	-0.30	0.689	6.97	-0.98	0.628
Dy ^{III}	7.65	-0.70	0.689	7.35	-1.00	0.662	7.78	-0.32	0.701	7.58	-0.52	0.683
Y ^{III}	7.54	-0.91	0.679	7.20	-1.25	0.649	7.73	-0.48	0.696	7.45	-0.76	0.671

(Values are accurate to ± 0.05)

Ternary systems : From the titration curves, formation of ternary complexes were found to occur in two step equilibria. In the first step, the ligand, A (IDA/NTA) forms binary complex, MA and in the second step, at higher pH region the ligand, L (HPBI/HPBO) interacts with the primary complex, MA leading to formation of the ternary complex, MAL. Thus HPBI/HPBO acts as secondary ligand.

In all the systems, distinct inflections were observed in the titration curves, indicating the nature of chelation. The formation of ternary complexes was further confirmed from

Fig. 1. Species distribution curves of Nd^{III}-NTA-HPBI ternary system the non-superimposable nature of the theoretical composite curves on the experimental curve in the region of ternary complex formation, change in intensity of colour of reaction mixture when compared to the corresponding binary systems. The species distribution curves (Figs. 1 and 2) generated using the computer program BEST also supports the formation of ternary complexes at higher pH region.

The formation constants of the ternary complexes have been evaluated⁸ and presented in Table 2. The relative stabilities of the ternary complexes, compared to the corresponding binary complexes were characterized in terms of the statistical parameter, $\Delta \log K$ and presented in Table 2.

Where,

$$\Delta \log K = \log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{ML}^M$$

The stabilities of the ternary chelates are also expressed in terms of basicity of the ligands i.e. stability per unit base strength (SUBS)⁹ and listed in the Table 2. Where,

$$SUBS = \log K_{MAL}^{MA} / \log \beta_n^H(L)$$

The results (Table 2) show that the ternary complexes are fairly stable. The negative values of $\Delta \log K$ show that the ternary complex, MAL formation is less favoured over the corresponding binary complex, ML. This may be due to the availability of lesser number of coordination sites for the secondary ligand, L on the primary complex, MA than on free metal ion¹⁰. The stabilities of the ternary complexes, MAL with respect to the ligand, A follow the order IDA > NTA. This can be due to effective charge neutralization and greater electrostatic interactions^{8,10} in the complex, M^{III}-IDA-L. The fully deprotonated IDA/NTA interact with the metal ion, M^{III} in the first step, followed by, HPBI/HPBO in the second step.

Since the [M-NTA-L]⁻ complex is negatively charged, the inter ligand repulsions may destabilize these complexes when compared to [M-IDA-L].

Fig. 2. Species distribution curves of Nd^{III}-IDA-HPBO ternary system

The stabilities of the ternary complexes with respect to the metal ion follow the order, $\text{La}^{\text{III}} < \text{Pr}^{\text{III}} < \text{Nd}^{\text{III}} < \text{Gd}^{\text{III}} < \text{Dy}^{\text{III}} > \text{Y}^{\text{III}}$. This order is in accordance with the ionic potentials/polarizabilities of the metal ions as a consequence of decrease in the ionic radius. This order is also in accordance with the SUBS of ligands in the ternary chelates.

Experimental

The ligands, HPBI and HPBO were prepared and purified by known procedures¹¹. The IDA, NTA, metal(III) salts, dioxane and other reagents used were of AnalaR grade. Doubly distilled water was used for all the experiments. Since HPBI and HPBO have limited solubility in water, their stock solutions were prepared in 1,4-dioxane. The stock solutions of metal ions, HNO_3 and KOH were standardized by known procedures¹². The pH-metric titration of 50 ml of acidified solution containing 1 : 1 : 1 (M : A : L) molar solution for ternary systems and 1 : 5 (M : L) for binary systems were carried out against carbonate free KOH solution in dioxane-water (50% v/v) medium at 30 °C and 0.1 M (KNO_3) ionic strength.

The proton-ligand (pK) and metal-ligand (ML and ML_2) binary formation constants were determined by Irving-Rossotti method⁶. The formation constants of ternary complexes (MAL) were evaluated⁸ and refined¹³. The species distribution curves at various pH values for the ternary systems were generated using the computer program BEST¹⁴. The pH-metric readings in dioxane-water were corrected by the method of Van Uitert and Haas¹⁵.

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